

INCREASING THERMAL PROTECTION OF ROOFING CONSTRUCTIONS OF RESIDENTIAL BUILDINGS.

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Abstract: This article discusses the issues of protecting the attic floor of low-rise residential buildings from heat and cold, the disadvantages of materials used in the protection, improving the thermal insulation properties. Today in private housing construction, the construction of houses with mansard and mansard roofs is very popular. The issue of protection and ventilation of such roofs from heat and cold is raised separately.

Key words: attics, thermal insulation, condensation, air permeability, thermal insulation, soffit

The main function of any roof is not only to protect the building from the effects of the atmosphere (rain, wind, sunlight, etc.), but also to prevent cooling of the upper floor rooms. Hot air always rises up, the air temperature under the ceiling is on average 2C higher than the floor temperature in the room. Therefore, when building a house, much attention is paid to the appearance of the roof, installation features, building materials. When it comes to improving the thermal protection of the roof, they understand low-rise apartment buildings with insulated mansard roofs and attics. For this type of house, the physical properties of the roof are very important, because the roof surrounds the room not only from above, but also from the sides.

The design of external enclosing structures must comply with the following thermal engineering requirements:

1. It should protect the premises from the cold in winter and autumn and have sufficient thermal properties to protect them from overheating in the summer sun.
2. Prevent the formation of very low temperatures on the inner surface during operation and prevent the formation of condensation;
3. Their air permeability should not exceed the permissible limit, greater air exchange cools the room;
4. Wet external barrier structures degrade thermal insulation properties and must maintain a normal humidity regime, taking into account their short-term nature.

70-80% of the thermal energy lost in the building is accounted for by external enclosing structures (walls, roof, floor, windows and doors), of which 15-20% is lost through the roof. Therefore, when erecting the roof, it is necessary to include

the ongoing work on its thermal insulation.

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According to construction calculations, the edge of the roof should be at least 50-60 centimeters away from the wall. This distance directly protects the facade of the building from moisture during rain and snow. The material used to seal this open space is called soffit.

Soffit is an Italian word meaning "sofito" - "shift". They are rigid and attached to each other, decorative panels made of aluminum, copper, vinyl or metal are used to cover the lower part of the roof protruding from the wall. Its function is not only to close, but also to ensure wind circulation at the bottom of the roof. Spotlights can be perforated or non-perforated. The wind passing through the holes ensures air circulation under the roof, prevents the formation of water vapor, and in the summer months the roof heats up, prevents excessive humidity of thermal insulation materials and corrosion of the roofing.

The correct execution of the attic layers also prevents excessive energy consumption. It is desirable to place basalt boards 150-200mm thick between the rafters, cover the bottom with a thermal insulation layer, cover the top with a thermal insulation layer and leave a gap of 50 mm. Only then, under the influence of moist air, water droplets do not form under the roof, the protective layers do not get wet and retain heat for a long time. Improper application of these layers leads to the formation of mold and mildew in the load-bearing structures, which, in turn, leads to premature failure.

Many experiments show that the most effective material for protecting mansard roofs from heat and cold is expanded polystyrene. At a density of 100 kg/m³, the thermal conductivity is 0.04 W/m°C. However, when it is installed, cracks remain at the joints with wooden structures, so mineral wool is widely used. Closing the crack seam will improve thermal protection in the future. One of

the main disadvantages of any mineral wool is a high level of water absorption (hygroscopicity). Therefore, when moisture gets into such a material, the thermal conductivity of mineral wool increases significantly, therefore, an increase in humidity by only 5% worsens the thermal insulation properties of the material by almost 50%. When the moisture entering the mineral wool freezes, the insulation may deform, which will further worsen its characteristics. Moisture does not linger in mineral wool for a long time, but evaporates, due to which it is used as a protective layer against heat loss from roofs, facades and floors.

For external and internal insulation of the roof, it is advisable to choose a basalt or fiberglass mineral wool insulation. The density of mineral wool for insulation of the roof should be at least 55 kg / m³, while the roof should not be too heavy to avoid overloading the load-bearing structures. The thickness of the layer is also important - about 15cm.

The interior cladding of the roof is mainly made of drywall sheets. It is desirable to assemble the internal parts along the rafters with drywall. The roof of the attic should also be insulated with the lower floor. If wooden beams are used as a partition, the distance from the mineral wool is equal to its height, and after the vapor barrier, a drywall ceiling is installed. The design and geometry of the roofs of the attic floors determine the basic shape of the building, which in turn means the need to create unity of structural and architectural solutions together with the interior space due to functional purpose. For attic floors, it is recommended to choose light materials, since on the one hand, they should be as simple as possible in delivery and installation, on the other hand, the specific weight of the structure should be minimal. For this purpose, the roof bases are chosen from wood and thin-walled metal profiles. It is not recommended to use stone and concrete materials for load-bearing roof structures. The cladding of the building must meet the same conditions, that is, it must be made mainly of light materials in the form of metal plates, metal tiles and the like. Where it is necessary to preserve the environment of existing buildings, the cladding is made of ceramic or cement-sand tiles, non-ferrous metals and other materials.

In short, any building, no matter what material it is made of, should be comfortable, cozy and moderate for people in the interior. There is still a lot to be done for this.

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